

A Study on Students Attitude Towards Entrepreneurship in Selective College From Coimbatore City

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ABSTRACT

The present article is an attempt that has been made to study the students 'attitude towards Entrepreneurship at Coimbatore City. Entrepreneurship is an area importance has raised multi fold over the last few decades around the world and in the last couple of decades in India. Entrepreneurship has become an everyday buzzword. Policymakers, economists, academics and even university students are talking about it. Seminars, Conferences and workshops are being organized every year across the world which emphasized on the importance of entrepreneurship to country, society as well as for the individual development. Today, there is big question raised in the minds of management students i.e., "Which way to go" either to go organizational development or to opt. Entrepreneurship as a career. It has been well recognized that the career choice is a very complicated and multifaceted process and will play a very important role in the life and development of students. To give a deep insight to answers those questions the current study is also discusses about the student's attitude towards Entrepreneur. What type of barriers they are facing while selecting entrepreneur as a career.

I. INTRODUCTION:

Entrepreneurship is the development of a business from the ground upcoming up with an idea and turning it into a profitable business. But while the definition of entrepreneurship may be simple, its execution is much more difficult. "Entrepreneurship is the journey of opportunity exploration and risk management to create value for profit and or social good. Gottlieb said that an entrepreneur is someone

who can take any idea, whether it be a product and/or service, and have the skill set, will and courage to take extreme risk to do whatever it takes to turn that concept into reality and not only bring it to market, but make it a viable product and/or service that people want or need.

An entrepreneur but there is certain characteristics that most successful entrepreneurs possess, Ability to plan

- Communication Skills
- Marketing skills
- Basic Management Skills
- Interpersonal Skills
- Leadership Skills

They are the risk taker and it is the prime motive that should be developed in the students. Students are the forth comer who can become an entrepreneur Entrepreneurship plays an important role in the rise and prosperity of a nation by cultivating the students and young entrepreneurs with innovation and entrepreneurial capacity, which enhances their competitiveness of employment and development under the circumstance of finance crisis. Successful entrepreneurs are those which always learn from their failures; which always tried to solve problems; tried to strength their weakness and make sure that this is what we actually want.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Many studies have revealed that entrepreneurs are not naturally conceived but made through their environment and experiences as they develop and

learn being impacted by guardian, mentors, tutors, instructors role model during their development process.

Many studies have revealed that entrepreneurs are not naturally conceived but made through their environment and experiences as they develop and learn, being impacted by guardian, mentors, tutors, instructors role model during their development process (Teixeira and Davey, 2008)[12]. The perspectives and believes of students toward entrepreneurship are the results of their immediate social and cultural environment. Consequently, the orientation and conducts of youth and young graduates are affected by various individual and ecological variables, which imply that the decision and desirability of becoming an entrepreneur or employee is a reflection of environmental and economic forces (Alain, Benoit and Clerc Narcissi 2006)[13]. Education about entrepreneurship and for entrepreneurship has the capacity of increasing students' interest in becoming entrepreneurs at some stage after completing their university degrees (Friendrich and Visser, 2005)[14]. Perceptions and attitudes of the youth towards entrepreneurship do vary among countries (Green & Pryde, 1990)[15]. In Canada, almost all the youth would like to start their own business some day but only half think they will, and the biggest barriers being fear of financial failures, lack of strong identity with the entrepreneurial role and lack of knowledge about the first step to take (Green and Pryde, 1990)[15].

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Present study is exploratory cum descriptive in nature. The sample size is 500 respondents. Data were collected from the selective colleges (BBA and MBA students) from Coimbatore city. Respondents participation was voluntarily & completely anonymous. Only those MBA & BBA students are consulted who are pursuing their course & doesn't include those students who have passed out.

IV. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- To analyze the factors influencing the students attitude towards entrepreneurship.
- To evaluate the perception level about the factors that led to the emergence of entrepreneurs in future period

V. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY:

The study is micro level and limited to only one department of Bharathiyar University, Coimbatore. This study is conducted bearing in mind the sample size of five hundred students. The management degree pursuing students of Bharathiyar University are the respondents which may not rationalize the survey as the view of students of other educational institute may differ. Because of bias and opinions of respondents, some responses of the questionnaire may differ from the reality.

VI. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Gender of The Respondents

From the above table 63% of the respondents were male and remaining 37% of them were female. Majority 63% of the respondents were male.

Age Group Of The Respondents

S.No	Age	Frequency	Percentage
1	Below 18	151	30.02
2	18-25	300	60.00
3	25-40	49	9.08
	Total	500	100.00

From the above table 60% of the respondents were 18-25 years, below 18 years or 30.2% and remaining 9.8% of them were 25-40. Majority 60% of the respondents belong to the age group of 18-25 years.

Educational Qualification Of The Respondents

S.No	Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
1	Graduation	236	47.02
2	Post graduation	109	28.08
3	Diploma	151	30.02
4	Others	4	8
	Total	500	100.00

From the above table 47.2% of the respondents have

completed school education, 30.2% of them have completed diploma, 28.8% of them have completed post graduate, and 8.8% of them completed others. Most 47.2% of the respondents have completed school education.

Course of The Respondents

S.No	Course	Frequency	Percentage
1	Commerce	264	52.08
2	Computer science	32	6.04
3	Management stream	27	5.04
4	Others	177	35.04
	Total	500	100.00

From the above table 52.8% of the respondents for commerce, 35.4% for computer science, 6.4% for management stream, and 5.4% for others. Majority 52.8% of the respondents for commerce.

Income of the Respondents

The monthly income of the respondents are 32% between Rs.15000-25000, 27% of a monthly income between above 35000, 23% of them had a monthly income between Rs.25000-35000, 16.6% of them had a monthly income below 15000.

IMPORTANCE OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP OF THE RESPONDENT:

S.NO	Importance of Entrepreneurship	Frequency	Percentage
1	Competency skill	197	39.03
2	Creativity	176	35.03
3	Empowerment	74	14.08
4	Self efficiency	49	9.08
	Total	500	100.00

From the above table 39.3% of the respondents were competency skill, 35.3% of them were creativity, 14.8% of them were empowerment, 9.8% of them were self efficiency with overall importance of entrepreneurship. 50.7% of the respondents were rank 1 as own boss, 35.3% of the respondents reported they want to be independent, 32.7% of respondents communicated to improve the society and 56.5% selected they would face barrier on selecting entrepreneurship, 66.7% feel positive on the opinion on selecting entrepreneurships.

VII. FINDINGS & SUGGESTION

The majorities of respondents was male and were in the age group between 18 to 25, their monthly income range between 15000 to 25000. Most of the respondents preferred to take self employment and become entrepreneurship and the motivating factor is towards entrepreneurship. The results provide that there is a significant relationship between age of the students and attitude towards entrepreneurship education. The scope level is higher in terms of economic growth and adaption of new technology.

SUGGESTION:

Entrepreneurial culture is common among a student. The Government, entrepreneurial supports programmers should take steps to motivate the students in the manufacturing sector with high innovativeness. The students are ready to face the challenges associated with entrepreneurship, have positive attitude towards entrepreneurship due to the regulations between self-employment and formal employment many of them are not ready to take entrepreneurship as their career choice. The study suggested that the students need to be given updates through entrepreneurial workshops and conferences in various fields to establish the new ventures in the future. The Government has to extend more support in diverse areas to entrepreneurial activities.

1) It was found that only 36 percent of the students were aware of any entrepreneurship development agencies. In order to create an entrepreneurial culture in campus it is necessary to create awareness about entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship development agencies. The institute should have tie-ups with

entrepreneurship development agencies to create awareness about entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial opportunities

2) Almost all the institutes surveyed (91 percent) had a placement cell in the campus, where only 65 percent institutes had an entrepreneurship development cell. Although the percent is satisfactory, the entrepreneurship development cell should be strengthened and prepare a calendar of activities to be conducted throughout the year.

CONCLUSION:

Based on the results above, there are a number of conclusions that can be given. First, students have a positive attitude towards entrepreneurship and they understand and appreciate the role the programmer plays in developing entrepreneurship knowledge and skills. Second, as a result of participation in the entrepreneurship education programme, many of the students show willingness to engage in entrepreneurship activities after completing schooling. Third, age and area of specialization have no influence on the attitude of students towards entrepreneurship education while gender has an influence. Fourth, challenges that have a potential of affecting the motivation of students to participate in entrepreneurship activities after completing school include accessing seed money as well as a lack of business opportunities. Finally, it is also concluded that legislation in Botswana is very conducive to the promotion of entrepreneurship activities.

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